

Performances of Cost-Effective 50G ONU with Analog FFE and HI-FEC

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Abstract: We propose a cost-effective 50G ONU reception scheme leveraging analog FFE and Hard-Input-FEC, achieving +3.8 dB of coding gain with analog FFE. This implementation reduces costs at ONUs compared to regular SI-FEC+DSP ones. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The 50 Gigabit capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) is the last technology proposed by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T) [1]. On the operator's side, an Optical Line Termination (OLT) connects up to 128 Optical Network Units (ONUs) over distances typically below 20 km. Due to the point-to-multipoint nature of the network, a Non-Return-to-Zero On-Off-Keying (NRZ-OOK) signal is broadcasted to all ONUs at a bitrate of 50 Gbit/s at 1342 nm in the Downstream (DS) and burst mode is required in the Upstream (US) for bitrates at 12.5, 25 or 50 Gbit/s at a wavelength of 1286 nm (case of the triple coexistence [2]). The 50G-PON is considerably challenged by the restricted bandwidths of low-cost commercially available transmitters and receivers often utilized from the datacenter market [3]) which cause severe InterSymbol Interference (ISI). To address these issues, equalization techniques have been integrated into PON specifications for the first time. Most of the community focused on Digital Signal Processing (DSP). In [4], the first real-time symmetrical 50G-PON prototype is presented, where a DSP-based Feed-Forward Equalizer (FFE) and Maximum Likelihood Sequence Estimation (MLSE) is used. Even if the DSP is more powerful (flexibility and adaptability) than the Analog Signal Processing (ASP) [5], it requires more resources: Serializer/Deserializer modules, parallelization, Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs) with very high sampling rates and so on, which means higher power consumption [6]. Recently, there has been a real and growing interest in ASP in PON with the first analog 50G-PON prototype being proposed in [7]. The first advantage of ASP is its very low power consumption [8] and it does not require ADC. However, the use of Analog FeedForward Equalizer (AFFE) implies taking into account its imperfections such as: limited bandwidth, taps distortion, non-linearity between taps and leakage of built-in amplifiers [9]. Equalization is not the only novelty brought by this new generation. More powerful Forward Error Correction (FEC) techniques have been chosen to allow for extra margins in terms of optical power budget at such high bit-rates. Compared to 10 Gigabit Symmetric capable Passive Optical Network (XGS-PON), FEC has also evolved from a simple Reed Solomon (RS) (255,239) to a more robust Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) (17280,14592) [10]. In [11], a Soft-Input LDPC and Hard-Input LDPC were implemented for real-time 50G-PON on an FPGA but the system was not tested over an optical transmission channel.

Fig. 1: ONU reception in the present case, with ADC, Clock Data Recovery (CDR), DSP and SI-FEC, and in the low-cost case with ASP, CDR, decision block and HI-FEC.

Several combinations of DSP/ASP and Soft-Input (SI)/Hard-Input (HI)-FEC are possible. This paper focuses on the comparison between two different combinations of equalization and FEC implementations for the ONU. Soft-Input FEC (SI-FEC) means that correction is made with an input belonging to the group of real numbers, whereas Hard-Input FEC (HI-FEC) correction is simply made with 1s and 0s. In this work, as represented on Fig. 1, we want to compare the ASP + HI-FEC solution, entitled cost-effective on Fig. 1, with the best possible case, i.e. ASP + SI-FEC, entitled reference ONU on Fig. 1. The issue with the reference ONU is that, while it would give better performance, it is too costly and expensive solution at the ONU side in DS. Adding an AFFE eliminates the need for an ADC, while promoting the choice of HI-FEC.

Fig. 2: Experimental setup.

2. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. A real-time Pulse Pattern Generator (PPG) generates a 50 Gbit/s NRZ-OOK signal based on a LDPC (17280,14592) codeword created from a PseudoRandom Binary Sequence (PRBS) 15 payload systematically encoded using the protograph matrix defined in [10]. The signal goes through an electrical amplifier (55 GHz bandwidth) and a bias-Tee is used to modulate an Electro-Absorption Modulator (EAM). The laser source consists of a Distributed FeedBack laser (DFB) followed by an EAM and then an Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (SOA), packaged in a Transmitter Optical Subassembly (TOSA) [12]. An Extinction Ratio (ER) of 7 dB and a mean output power of 13.3 dBm under modulation is measured. The DFB, EAM and SOA biases are respectively fixed to 140 mA, -1.7 V and 100 mA. The TOSA is regulated at room temperature (24 °C) with a Thermo-Electrical Cooler (TEC). The signal goes through up to 25 km of Standard Single Mode Fiber (SSMF) with a dispersion range of 76.1 ps/nm at 1342±2 nm, which is close to the worst case (77.1 ps/nm) defined at the ITU-T [1]. A Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) and a powermeter ("Pm" on Fig. 2) is used to assess performances for different optical budgets. Opto-Electrical conversion is performed with a 25G-class Ge/Si Avalanche PhotoDiode (APD) with an embedded TransImpedance Amplifier (TIA) [13]. An AFPE of 6 taps spaced of 7.5 ps is used to equalize the signal. The AFPE parameters are optimized by capturing the TIA output signal with an Real-Time Oscilloscope (RTO) (100 GSa/s and 33 GHz bandwidth) and then applying the algorithm presented in [9]. Since our FEC decoding is not performed real-time, we use 100 GSa/s and 200 GSa/s acquisitions from an RTO to recreate a continuous-time equivalent version of the received signal which will be fed to the decoder. This signal is upsampled to 16 samples/symbol ("OVS" in Fig. 2). After acquisition, we perform offline synchronization, slicing and decoding. Two FEC decoding approaches are evaluated here. In the first one, soft inputs are given to the decoder. This corresponds to the best case in terms of performance but the worst in terms of complexity and cost since the decoder uses real-valued samples to search for the transmitted sequence. In the second approach, a less performing but also less complex HI-FEC approach is used where error correction is performed using only the information on the signs of the received sequence. We use an iterative layered weighted minsum decoder with a weight factor of 0.75 and a maximum of 14 iterations. Bit Error Rate (BER) curves are measured before and after equalization (except after FEC) with an Error Detector (ED). Eye diagrams are measured with a Digital Communication Analyzer (DCA) (50 GHz bandwidth).

3. Results

Results are shown on Fig. 3 where BER curves are represented as a function of the Received Optical Power (ROP). Fig. 3a corresponds to SI-FEC while Fig. 3b corresponds to HI-FEC. From the curves before equalization (blue dots) and the curves after equalization (dotted orange dots) without FEC, we can see that the algorithm has been able to converge on a solution that improves signal quality by equalizing the Chromatic Dispersion (CD) and the limited bandwidth of components. This is confirmed by Fig. 3c and Fig. 3d, which show the eye diagram before and after equalization respectively. The eye after the AFPE is more open, facilitating decision. The AFPE can be considered to have two main functions: equalization and amplification, since after bandwidth enhancement, it amplifies the signal. Without FEC, we obtain a sensitivity for a BER at 10^{-2} of -24.4 dBm (without AFPE) and -25.7 dBm (with AFPE), i.e. an improvement of 1.3 dB. The use of LDPC FEC allows us to obtain waterfall profiles for the post-FEC BER curves. As a result, we can first demonstrate that LDPC works as expected. The blue squares curve corresponds to the post-FEC without AFPE, while the dotted orange squares curve corresponds to the post-FEC with AFPE. For reasons of processing time, we have limited the transmission to 270 codewords. This low number of codewords does not allow us to obtain an *error free* which is defined for a BER of 10^{-12} in the standard [10] but gives us a good idea on the position of the post-FEC waterfalls. FEC curves are extrapolated to derive the trend. Based on the sharp slope of the FEC curves, we can obtain a good estimate of the sensitivity obtained at post-FEC to obtain an *error free* regime, assumed here to be obtained for BER values below 10^{-8} in our experiment. Looking at the SI-FEC on Fig. 3a, without the AFPE, we obtain a sensitivity of -25.8 dBm, giving us an coding gain of +8.1 dB at a BER 10^{-4} . The coding gain is the difference between pre- and post-FEC

Fig. 3: Performance before (blue curves) and after equalization (orange dotted curves) without (dots) and with FEC at the 14th iteration (squares) for a) SI-FEC and b) HI-FEC as a function of ROP. Eye diagrams c) before and d) after AFPE for a ROP of -15 dBm.

power in dB. The post-FEC waterfall is not affected by the BER floor observed pre-FEC due to ISI. Compared with the HI-FEC, the coding gain is better, as HI-FEC's gain is +7.1 dB (sensitivity of -24.8 dBm), see on Fig. 3b. This is to be expected, as HI-FEC is less efficient than SI-FEC in that it only considers binary values (0 or 1) after comparing the received signal with a fixed threshold. Any accurate information on the signal's confidence level is ignored in this case, making this method less effective at correcting errors than the SI-FEC. By adding an AFPE, both with SI-FEC and HI-FEC, we see an improvement in coding gain of +4.8 dB and +3.8 dB for SI-FEC (sensitivity of -27.8 dBm) and HI-FEC (sensitivity of -27 dBm) respectively. Overall, the results obtained under the same conditions (with and without AFPE) with SI-FEC are better than HI-FEC. However, when an AFPE is added to an HI-FEC, performance is better than SI-FEC without AFPE (-27 dBm with AFPE + HI-FEC compared to -25.8 dBm with SI-FEC only) which is more than enough for what is defined in the standard in terms of received optical power [1, 10].

4. Conclusion

This study presents a cost-effective 50G ONU solution employing analog FFE and HI-FEC, enabling high-performance transmission and reducing complexity and costs for the DS ONU. We compare two solutions: one considering ASP with SI-FEC, corresponding to a reference ONU, and one considering ASP with HI-FEC, which is considered as a cost-effective ONU. By simplifying the architecture of the ONU, i.e. by choosing to use an HI-FEC, we get performance that is not as good as SI-FEC, but good enough to be compliant with the standard. We obtained coding gains of +8.1 dB and +7.1 dB (BER of 10^{-4}) for SI-FEC and HI-FEC without AFPE and a sensitivity of -24.8 dBm and -24.8 dBm respectively. Adding AFPE, we obtain an encoding gain of +4.8 dB and +3.8 dB and a sensitivity of -27.8 dBm and -27 dBm respectively for SI-FEC and HI-FEC. In this way, we have shown that it is possible to reduce ONU costs and energy consumption for 50G-PON by adding ASP with HI-FEC, making it more efficient than a SI-FEC alone, and thus avoiding the complexity and cost of the DSP. We show that with a sensitivity threshold of 10^{-2} as defined in the standard, we are well within the waterfall zone.

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